

[Willow Creek Capital Partners, L.P.](#) is a privately owned hedge fund sponsor which investment vehicles and separate accounts (SMAs) focus on publicly traded U.S. equities.

It invest in undervalued stocks of companies, while focusing equally on flawed companies to engage in short sales by employing a market neutral approach and a long/short equity strategy. In order to generate a bottom up stock picking approach for constructing its portfolios the firm utilizes fundamental analysis.

This investment management firm is based in Greenbrae, California and it was founded in April 1995. It has decades-long track record of success and works with dozens of inspiring investors and business-builders during Willow Creek Capital Partners, L.P.'s existence.

Willow Creek Capital Partners, L.P. invests in companies that are undervalued by utilizing a disciplined process that measures risk (downside) while identifying the catalysts for increasing value. It purposefully engages only in friendly transactions and works with talented management teams.

Willow Creek Capital Partners, L.P. strives to assist companies in which it has the purpose to invest. Its aim is to improve their results across varied elements of a business's operations thereby attempting to help to maximize value.

Willow Creek Capital Partners L.P. bases on the skills and experience of its employees and consults other like-minded investors. It has the aim to deliver superior long-term and risk-adjusted performance while invests in undervalued stocks of small-cap and mid-cap companies.

To maximize efficiency, Willow Creek Capital Partners L.P. has established a formal governing process and an efficient operational structure, utilizing "outsourcing" of all non-investment functions whenever possible.

[This company](#) has built long-term relationships with a number of reputable service providers that specialize in fund accounting and administration, securities laws and regulations, audit and tax, and technology.